

STRATEGIC PLANNING FOR HUMAN RESOURCES AND ITS IMPACT ON ORGANIZATIONAL AGILITY BY APPLICATION TO THE UNIVERSITY OF BAGHDAD

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Abstract

The goal of the study was to investigate how strategic planning contributes to organizational agility at the University of Baghdad. This relationship was examined in terms of short-term and long-term planning practices, as well as scenario analysis and SWOT analysis, as independent variables, with organizational agility at the University of Baghdad serving as a dependent variable. The results are proven at a moral level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) a correlation and impact between strategic planning and organizational agility of the University of Baghdad, as well as a correlation and impact between planning practices using scenario analysis and organizational agility at the University of Baghdad, and an correlation and impact between planning practices using sowt analysis and organizational agility, short and long planning practices and organizational agility at a moral level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). One of the most important suggestions of the study is the need for banks to spread the culture of strategic planning to all levels of organizational and human beings. In order for universities to apply strategic planning according to planning axes using scenario analysis, Planning using sowt analysis, short and long term planning, enhancing its organizational agility by focusing on confirming the ease and speed of decision-making in light of the developments facing Iraq's university sector.

Keywords: strategic planning - scenario analysis - SOWT- short and long term planning - organizational agility - University of Baghdad.

Introduction.

Institutions face many challenges that require them to strengthen their practices from the point of view of human resources management, especially since the human element is the important focus in overcoming these challenges through policies and practices carried out by the human resources department so that the organization responds to comply with the changes in the internal and external work environment. These challenges were reflected in the need to develop human resource management practices, taking into account the strategic dimensions affecting the work environment at the internal and external levels, as many studies have highlighted this.

These models also came in the light of contemporary considerations in the science of administrative organization that focus on achieving flexibility and agility in administrative organization and its various procedures and operations, which requires that there be appropriate organizational flexibility that enables government institutions to conform to and overcome these challenges, as we find that recent literature touched on To the term organizational agility, which focuses on achieving speed and ease in the organizational performance of institutions, especially in facing challenges, making sound decisions, and employing their core capabilities and benefiting from them properly.

To achieve this, it is required that there be a prominent role for the organizational units in the structure of the institution, especially the human resources management, and the various roles and practices that it performs, which undoubtedly affect the performance of individuals and their roles towards all the modern methods applied by the institution and adopting the best practices through which it works to develop performance And improve it and reach the desired levels of quality and excellence, leading to the desired and effective organizational agility. Therefore, the current study will focus on evaluating the impact of strategic planning for human resources on organizational agility by applying it to the University of Baghdad.

Research problem.

The researcher's awareness of the research question stems from his exposure to previous research on "Strategic Planning for Human Resources and its Impact on Organizational Flexibility", as well as what the researcher drew from readers and analysis of previous strategic research on human resource management and related matters. Models in which the role of human resource management is embodied in responding to the external environment through the design of appropriate policies, and a prominent role in achieving organizational strategic compatibility.

Previous studies of organizational agility have also reinforced that it requires presence and speed in the organizational structure and immediate response to unexpected changes. It also requires adapting to the challenges and dynamic changes that appear quickly, which impose on the organization as well as the presence of competencies in the role and tasks performed by employees for the smooth flow of work procedures and the flow of procedures easily between units. The organizational structure of the institution, as well as the development of the work environment and human resources in line with the required organizational agility), and then the problem of the research study centers on answering the following main question-:

What is the impact of strategic planning for human resources on the organizational agility of employees at the University of Baghdad?

Importance search.

The importance of this study lies in its originality, as it is one of the most important studies in the field of human resources and management, and within the knowledge of researchers, it discusses the topic of "strategic planning in human resources and management". Its impact on organizational flexibility through its presentation to the University of Baghdad "If we proceed

from the famous epistemological principles" every important scientific thought. The significance of this study was determined as follows:

1. The theoretical importance of this study stems from the importance of strategic planning for human resources, as it is a recent theoretical trend in the literature of human resources management, and it is also related to the theoretical importance of this study, which shows the scientific dimension of these models and what that is. They rely on basic knowledge.
2. The academic importance of this study stems from the importance of the strategic planning variables included in the current study in scenario analysis, planning using SOWT analysis, and short and long-term planning practices, which need to be strengthened in the Arab context.
3. The practical importance also stems from the fact that the current study presents proposals that may benefit the government banking sector in improving its use of strategic planning tools in terms of scenario analysis method, planning using SOWT analysis, and short and long-term planning practices.
4. The current study also acquires its importance from a scientific angle related to the importance of the issue of organizational agility as it is one of the modern topics in the science of administrative organization, which contributes to enriching the Arab library in this field.
5. The importance of the applied study also stands out in that it can make contributions that help draw attention to the importance of applying the dimensions of strategic human resource management models, and the procedures that help in their practical application.
6. Provide contributions that can help to apply organizational agility in appropriate ways to effectively improve institutional performance.
7. The results of this study can help decision makers at the University of Baghdad and its affiliated departments to develop new policies and activate strategic planning tools for human resources.

Research Objectives: This research aims to identify the impact of strategic planning for human resources on organizational agility. The following sub-objectives emerge from this objective:

1. Testing the significance of the relationship between planning practices using scenario analysis, which led to achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.
2. Foreseeing the moral relationship between planning practices using SOWT analysis, which led to achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.
3. Study and determine the moral and essential relationship between short and long-term planning practices, which led to achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.

Research questions:

1. What is the role of planning practices using scenario analysis in achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad?
2. What is the role of planning practices using SOWT analysis in achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad?
3. What is the role of short- and long-term planning practices in achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad?

Research hypotheses.The current study is based on testing the validity of the following research assumptions:

1. The first hypothesis: It is possible that strategic planning practices lead to achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.
2. The second hypothesis: The more planning practices using the scenario, the more this leads to achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.
3. The third hypothesis and sub-hypothesis: the more planning practices increase in SOWT analysis, the more this leads to achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.
4. The fourth hypothesis: The more short- and long-term planning practices increase, the more this leads to achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.

Search model and variables: The researcher also explains the relationships of the research hypotheses variables in the following figure:-

Theoretical framework and previous studies:

Strategic planning is one of the most important types of long-term future planning, which is the starting point for young people, through a holistic strategy; In an effort to move towards the desired situation, thanks to its features and characteristics that distinguish it from other types, and the ability of planning to put young people in a position of competition and distinction from others, so it is a goal that cannot be ignored or neglected; If the planning is

based on sound foundations and clear visions within a clear vision, mission and strategic objectives; The output will meet the desired ambitions.

The concept of strategic planning for human resources

The concept of strategic planning is considered one of the most important administrative concepts that have received approval and spread in recent years, as it was known that strategic planning is an advanced stage of the development of the planning system in general. (Al-Abadi, 2018, p. 33)

It was also defined as the process of making continuous decisions based on possible information about the future of these decisions and their effects in the future. (Al-Hadrawi, 2016, p. 295)

The researcher defines it procedurally as a long-term scientific planning that aims to find effective strategies that seek to improve and develop the teaching and learning processes, with all they include in terms of curriculum, means, teaching methods, students, teachers, and educational administration.

While human resource management is defined as “all the administrative activities related to determining the organization’s human resource needs, developing its capabilities and raising its efficiency, and granting it compensation, motivation and full care for its sake, with the aim of achieving the organization’s objectives and making the most of its effort (Abrah, 2017)

- He defined strategic planning for human resources: the process by which the required human resources are provided in terms of quantity, quality, time and place to achieve national interests at the general level and the interests of institutions at the private level, by bringing about the mental and moral development of individuals, including the provision of trained cadres at the global level, academically Technically and technically, forming national behavior and institutional professional behavior, strengthening belonging to the institution, building correct personal behavior and imbuing it with virtuous values, and establishing partnership between educational and training institutions.
- It was also known as the way in which the organization's need for human resources is determined for the current and future phases in terms of determining the qualifications and numbers required. (Al-Mahasna, 2016, pg. 203)

It is also known as the process that includes the organization's prediction of the demand for its human resources, analysis of the supply of these resources, and then developing strategies to reduce the gap between them that contribute to reaching the appropriate numbers and types of human resources to reach efficient work that contributes effectively to reaching the economic sustainability of these organizations. (Al-Mahasna, 2016, pg. 203)

- The researcher defines strategic planning for human resources procedurally: it is the formulation of human resources strategies that are compatible with environmental opportunities, business strategies and organizational structure in order to achieve competitive advantages by the human element to achieve the goals of the institution, and

it will be measured in this study through the following dimensions (job analysis - polarization - evaluation performance - training - motivation).

Objectives of strategic planning:

There is a set of goals that strategic planning seeks to achieve, and these goals are as follows:

1. Determines the prevailing culture in the institution - The strategic planning of the community provides an accurate description of the educational institution
2. .Strategic planning gives a clear idea of the direction and objectives of the educational institution.
3. Strategic planning serves as a criterion for formulating the policy pursued by the institution.
4. Creates strategic planning motivation and speaking among the members of the institution.
5. Strategic planning makes the conduct of affairs in education not limited to senior managers, but rather involves many individuals from inside and outside the educational institution. Strategic planning achieves a balance between short-term and long-term goals.(Al-Hadrawi, 2016, p. 317).

Objectives of Strategic Planning:

1. Training of managers.
2. Set more realistic goals.
3. Improving communication and human relations.
4. Directing the attention of senior management to strategic issues.
5. Providing the necessary information and data for the senior management to make better decisions.
6. Achieving better coordination between the organization's activities.
7. Tightening the control over the operations within the institution.
8. Analyze the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats facing the organization.
9. It makes the focus of human, financial and material resources on the important things in the organization (the most important and then the important), while directing departments and research to develop new graduates.
10. Developing a sense of security among managers due to their understanding of the changing environment, and their willingness to adapt to it. (Al-Abadi, 2018, pg. 42)

Concept of agility:

The origin of the word gracefulness in the Arabic language goes back to the verb “throwing with embracing, gracefulness. Discipline: it is said to the boy and the maid if they are in moderation: graceful and graceful, and they throw graceful. And graceful elegance: light and fast.” (Al-Hadrawi, 2016, p. 298)

The concept of agility is a modern concept in the current contemporary management thought, as there are a large number of different terms around this concept; The concept of organizational agility emerged as a term used in research at the beginning of 1991 when a group of researchers at the (Inocco) Institute, at Lahigh University in the United States called for it to develop a comprehensive definition of educational agility that includes all important aspects and dimensions. This is through their study that they conducted at that time entitled “Strategies of Manufacturing Enterprises in the Twenty-first Century from the Point of View of Industry Experts.” (D Dursun., A Zeynep, E. C, 2018, p85)

And idiomatically defined: it is a type of flexibility, which is the ability to find new activities and unplanned actions, in response to unexpected shifts, and organizational agility is defined as agility within the organization and rapid response to changes in the work environment surrounding it in order to achieve its goals, through Through adaptation and flexibility in dealing with it quickly and effectively. (Mahmoud, 2021, p. 41)

Abdel Razek (2018) defined organizational agility as the organization’s ability to sense the expected and unexpected changes that occur in its internal and external work environment (which are complex, intertwined and emphatic) provided that sensing is accompanied by the organization developing an innovative and dynamic response to those changes by re-designing processes, Re-allocation of organizational resources, and reshaping of organizational structures to enhance the organization's ability to survive and survive in the business world and support its competitive position. (Abdel-Razek, 2018, p. 223)

It is also referred to as the organization's ability to reshape its strategy in the current environment by anticipating and constantly adapting to customer requirements and needs. mon., L Fiona., L, 2016, p90) .

The researcher believes that despite the large number and multiplicity of definitions of organizational agility, they emphasize a set of capabilities that contribute to enabling the organization to adapt to changes and exploit new opportunities in order to gain the organization a competitive advantage, and it is clear from the above, that the concept of organizational agility if applied in the field University education, as it may contribute to increasing the educational institution’s ability to sense expected and unexpected changes in the work environment, whether internal or external, and quickly respond to them, and deal with them effectively and innovatively.

Hence, the researcher defines organizational agility procedurally: rapid response to changes and threats surrounding the organization and responding successfully to the opportunities available to it and dealing with them effectively and innovatively in a way that enhances the

organization's ability to survive and continue, and it will be measured in this study through the following dimensions (sensing agility - agility decision-making - agility practice.)

The importance of organizational agility and its objectives:

Organizational agility is one of the basic requirements for organizations to ensure their survival and sustainability, and it is considered a sustainable advantage. It is difficult to choose the best of them.

Organizational agility enables organizations to carry out a series of specific tasks under an open management system that senses and manages opportunities and risks frozen in activities leading to new innovations. Therefore, organizational agility is of great importance in organizations that arrive in a rapidly changing environment, where there are increasingly systemic internal relationships that make the business environment increasingly complex, as contemporary administrative challenges emerge in how to coordinate these systemic relationships, as well as in How to build administrative systems. (Bani Hani, 2021, p. 56)

Dimensions of organizational agility

There are three types of organizational agility, and as indicated by the studies reviewed by the researcher, which correspond to the importance and objectives of the current research, and these dimensions can be clarified through the following:

1. **Sensing Agility:** It is the organizational ability to examine, monitor and capture inter-change events "change in customer preferences, new competitor movements, and new technologies in a timely manner. Organizational, competitive work, and future performance. The task of sensing includes activities such as obtaining information related to events, in which environmental change is manifested, and purifying it from unimportant information depending on the foundations.
2. **Speed of Decision:** The ability to collect, aggregate, structure, and evaluate relevant information from a variety of sources in order to interpret the business impact of an incident in a timely manner, identify threats based on the interpretation of the incident, and develop action plans to guide how resources are reallocated.
3. **Agency velocity:** is the ability to reconfigure organizational resources, modify operations, launch new products and services, and new market models in a timely manner. A business task consists of a series of activities to regroup organizational resources and adjust business operations according to actual conditions. The resulting business principles emerge from the task of making a decision to respond to environmental change (Al Wakeel, 2022, p. 282)

The basics of organizational agility in university education institutions: There are several elements that may contribute to achieving organizational agility in university education institutions, which are:

1. The existence of a clear strategy that defines the vision and mission of the educational institution and the most important strategic objectives that it seeks to achieve is not

sufficient to achieve organizational agility. The leadership of the university must develop this strategy in partnership with all staff (faculty and staff), giving them a real opportunity to participate in the development of the strategy, providing the right input, and encouraging the use of brilliant minds; This ensures that everyone actively seeks out, engages with the university's leadership and works with its leaders to implement this strategy once it is approved.

2. Defining strategies allows an accurate understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of educational institutions, understanding the opportunities available to them, exploiting them, identifying threats in the external environment and transforming them into real opportunities, and then creating new competitive advantages so that educational institutions are smart. and effective response to changes around you; Adapt to the latest developments and make better progress based on the depth of changes taking place around you. (Abdul Razek 2018 p. 215)

3. Take advantage of information technology:

Information technology is one of the most important resources to support organizational agility; It provides the opportunity to learn about the most important local or global changes and developments in the shortest possible time, and provides access to any information or access to educational institutions that you need. To make specific decisions that enable them to respond quickly to understand the changes occurring around them and act accordingly. or between them and the corresponding educational institutions, linking them and allowing the exchange of information and experiences between them; This ensures the ease and mobility of the data and information people need at work, provides them with greater flexibility and consistency, coordinates across different functional levels, and supports organizational agility.

4. Create flexible network organizational structures:

The availability of a flexible networked organizational structure, which relies on technology to communicate with each other and move away from traditional hierarchies, may help to respond quickly to changes or developments in an efficient and timely manner, and thus support the achievement of organizational flexibility, as flexible and agile organizational structures improve the ability of The organization helps to take appropriate actions and decisions at the right time, and provides university leaders with the opportunity to closely understand what is happening in middle management through cooperation and encouragement of internal activities within departments and between different functional levels within educational institutions, and overcoming the obstacles that may face them in achieving specific strategic goals.

5. Participation in decision-making and support for decentralization:

In order for educational institutions to enjoy organizational agility; It is important for the participation of various individuals from: faculty members and employees in making decisions related to them or related to the future of their educational institutions, as the

presence of a dynamic mutual interaction between them and university leaders increases their effectiveness, raises their morale, and ensures a rational and sound decision is reached, and even faster implementation and giving Some of the powers of individuals working at the executive levels, such as delegated authority and giving them the opportunity to make decisions, thus, it becomes clear the importance of.

6. The competence of individuals in educational institutions:

Individuals who work in educational institutions must have an appropriate level of competence, and have many skills that qualify them to work in their job duties, make them able to deal with change, and have the ability to learn everything new and develop their abilities; To constantly improve themselves, it is also important to emphasize the importance of communicating with each other to exchange and transfer experiences, enhance their ability to take responsibility, provide ways and methods that help them deal with all challenges, take advantage of them for the benefit of the educational institution, and take care of meeting their needs; To achieve their job satisfaction, which will positively affect the speed of completion of work.

7. Providing a supportive climate for innovation and experimentation with new and distinctive ideas:

There must be an organizational culture that supports innovation, encourages initiative and confidence, and introduces new things without hesitation

Previous studies:

Previous studies represent an important source for the researcher when conducting his study and he must see it before proceeding with the design of his study, in order to enable him to crystallize the study problem, its objectives and hypotheses and help him in preparing the theoretical framework, so this part deals with previous studies related to the subject of the study, and these studies can be classified into two axes As follows:

The study of Bani Hani (2021) aimed to identify the impact of human resources strategies (analysis, selection, training, evaluation) on organizational agility (sensing agility, decision-making agility, and practice agility) in commercial banks in Jordan. The study was conducted at all levels (senior management, middle management) in commercial banks in Jordan, which numbered (13), and the questionnaire was distributed to the representative sampling unit (director, assistant manager, department head, branch manager, assistant branch manager) out of (320)

The most important findings of the study are that there is a positive impact of human resource strategies in terms of their combined dimensions (analysis, selection, training, evaluation) on organizational agility in terms of their combined dimensions (sensing agility, decision-making agility, agility of practice) in Jordanian commercial banks.

The study recommended the need for the management of commercial banks to pay attention to human resource strategies by making a guide to the requirements of the work of each job to facilitate identification of their needs of human resources that help achieve competitive

advantage, and to strive and pay attention to agility, sensing and decision-making by conducting a periodic evaluation of the potential effects that occur in the external environment on its activity to increase the ability to Detecting changes in the movements of his competitors and saving them in the database for ease of action using modern methods of work, and discovering the creativity of workers who have the ability to create a competitive advantage to keep pace with changes in the markets.

Al-Wakeel study (2022) sought to examine the role of strategic planning in achieving organizational agility in government banks in Egypt, and focused on this relationship in terms of planning practices using scenario analysis, planning practices using SOWT analysis, short and long-term planning practices, as independent variables, organizational agility in banks. Government in Egypt is a dependent variable.

The results came to prove at a significant level that there is a correlation and impact relationship between strategic planning and organizational agility in government banks in Egypt. , Short and long planning practices and organizational agility at a moral level. One of the most important things suggested by the study is the need for banks to spread the culture of strategic planning at all organizational and human levels, for banks to work on applying strategic planning according to planning axes using scenario analysis, planning using SOWT analysis, Short and long-term planning, enhancing its organizational agility by focusing on confirming the ease and speed of decision-making, the speed of application of techniques and technology in its banking services, and the speed of adjusting its internal banking operations, in light of the developments facing the Egyptian banking sector.

Krzysztof and Raoul (2019) study focused on strategic planning focusing on the areas of risks and hedging for sudden changes in the areas of the institution's work, while working on developing the capabilities of the institution and employing them in the best way.

The study (2019) Jennifer and Neal observed that the role of strategic planning is based on developing an effective plan for the organization that enables it to develop organizational and human performance, and to translate strategic goals into executive work mechanisms and appropriate operational plans to transform goals into reality.

Commentary on previous studies

In light of the review of previous studies, the researcher concluded the following:

- Previous studies contributed to shedding light on strategic planning for human resources and its importance in enhancing organizational agility.
- Some previous studies were assigned to strategic planning for human resources and organizational agility, but they did not address the variables that were developed in this study in one study.
- The current study agreed with previous studies in using the descriptive approach and the questionnaire as a tool for data collection, but it differed with some studies in terms of the study sample and the human and spatial scope of the study.

- The human resource is considered one of the most important resources that can contribute to achieving comprehensive development, not only at the level of the organization, but at the level of society in all its organs and institutions.
- The great importance in contemporary administrative thought of the necessity of the integration and interaction of the organization's strategy as a whole, and the surrounding external environment and how it confronts the various variables.
- There is a scarcity to some extent in the studies that dealt with considering human resources as one of the important strategies through which some concepts can be used to support the strategy of the organization as a whole, and use them in the organizational agility of the organizations under application. Presenting a set of recommendations that can guide those in charge of human resources management in the universities under study in developing human resources strategies in their universities to reduce the negative effects of contemporary challenges and gain competitive advantages.
- Accordingly, the research gap on which the current study was based is that the previous studies did not seek to address the impact of the effectiveness of strategic planning functions for human resources in universities, as it was found that there is a clear shortcoming in the previous studies, which is what the current study seeks to achieve.

Field study:

Research Methodology.

The researcher used the descriptive analytical approach in order to build a theoretical scientific rooting in the study of the topic of the dimensions of the relationship of strategic planning with organizational agility at the University of Baghdad. Developing a questionnaire that includes a number of dimensions, namely strategic planning using SOWT analysis, short and long-term planning, and organizational agility.

Research community and sample.

It represents the research community at the University of Baghdad, where the researcher used a comprehensive inventory method for officials and employees from the human resources department, administrative development, structures and services at the University of Baghdad, which numbered (280) items from the complete sample population.

Data collection tools.

The researcher conducted a field study using:

- Survey form: on a deliberate sample of (280) individual employees at the University of Baghdad in all its departments, in order to agree with the general objective of the study, which is to identify the study of strategic planning for human resources and its impact on agility by applying to the University of Baghdad (the study sample). The research is divided into two layers, and they are (higher, supervisory), provided that the vast majority of the sample is from the executive level, as it is the level most affected by strategic planning.

•Inspection unit:

The sampling unit was represented in the research through the employees of the University of Baghdad, who are responsible for human resources management, administrative and structural development, and educational services.

Table No: 1 Distribution of the study sample

Percentage of the total sample size	Sample volume	the groups subject to the study sample
%30	60	Department Managers
%70	220	employees
%100	280	Totals

Research tool design.

The researcher developed the study tool in light of reference to some previous studies in the field of strategic planning and organizational agility, where the researcher puts this through the following table-:

Table No: 2

Ratio of axis statements from tool statements	Number of phrases	axis called	hub
%22,4	11	Planning axis using scenario	first
%24,5	12	plotting axis using swot analysis	Second
%24,5	12	Short- and long-term planning	Third
%28,6	14	The focus of organizational agility	fourth
%100	49	total	

The sampling method and the application of the research tool

The researcher applied the study tool and distributed it in the departments of the University of Baghdad, in addition to identifying and providing communication tools such as telephone and e-mail, which belong to the researcher to respond to any inquiries about the questionnaire, and to ensure that the officials' appointments are appropriate to receive the questionnaire and respond to it at a time convenient for them.

Validity and reliability of the research tool

Honesty means the extent to which the research tool is able to measure the topic for which it was developed, meaning to what degree is the data collection tool valid. The data collection tool is suitable for measuring the purpose for which it was placed so that it does not measure something else or mean something else besides it, and the validity was made according to the following-:

1. Face Validity: It is related to the apparent or superficial honesty of the research tool, through which the tool and data collection statements related to each of the axes are judged in terms of their relation to the field and topic of the research, the extent of the clarity and suitability of the tool to

the research sample, the validity of the order of phrase items and their validity to obtain Answers from the research sample, and this test was conducted by a sample of the research community.

2. Content Validity: This type of validity depends on the validity of the content in terms of the representation of the expressions for the research variables and their coverage of the topic. The following:

Getman's equation = (errors number.1)/ (number of respondents x number of questions)

(1The validity of the arbitrators: where the research tool was presented to a group of specialized arbitrators, in order to confirm the aspects of form, wording, arrangement, safety of measurement statements and their suitability.

2) Stability of the tool: Here, the stability means that the tool gives the same results if it is used or repeated again under similar conditions, as it was calculated through the coefficient (Alpha Cro-Nbach), using the statistical program (spss), where the following table shows a value for each axis, as well as the overall stability of the tool.

Table No. 3: Alpha coefficient of internal consistency of the search tool

Alpha. Stability Coefficient	axis called	hub
0.834	Planning axis using scenario	first
0.866	plotting axis using swot analysis	Second
0.882	Short- and long-term planning	Third
0.821	The focus of organizational agility	fourth
0.851	Overall stability and internal consistency of the tool	

Sources and Limits of Research:

The research data was obtained through two inputs, which we explain as follows:-

A) Secondary sources: they relate to books, periodicals, magazines, bulletins, research, and Arabic and English statistics related to the issue of strategic planning and organizational agility.

b) Primary sources: which are represented in the research tool such as the questionnaire form that was distributed to the research sample representing the community.

The limits of the research will be limited to the following aspects:-

-Human limits: the research sample focused on officials and employees from the human resources department, administrative development, structures and services at the University of Baghdad.

Objective limits: The current study was limited to addressing the dimensions of strategic planning in terms of three main dimensions, namely planning using scenario analysis, planning using SOWT, and short and long-term planning, as independent variables, as for the dependent variable in organizational agility.

Statistical analysis:

The current study used SPSS computer applications in order to conduct the necessary analysis of the data of the questionnaire forms, through the following statistical tools:

Variance analysis.

Kendall's correlation coefficient.

-coefficient of determination R² regression analysis

Matrix of correlation coefficients for search variables.

Applied study and analysis of the relationships between the variables of strategic planning and organizational agility:

In this aspect of the applied study, which seeks to achieve the objectives of the study and test the hypotheses, where the questionnaire was prepared and confirmed its credibility and stability, and the research sample was described, as well as the tests of the correlation matrix between the research variables, as well as the Pearson correlation coefficient test and the coefficient of determination r² using the SPSS program, and the researcher notes Here, the validity of the responses contained in the distributed questionnaires was reviewed and confirmed, confirmed and prepared in preparation for converting them into a “quantitative” scale that can be entered into the SPSS statistical analysis program. The five-point Likert scale was also used and a weight was given to each level of the scale according to the following:

Very Agree (5), Agree (4), Neutral (3), Disagree (2), Very Disagree (1), and enter the data into the program according to these weights and encode the measurement statements and responses, in order to measure the correlation coefficients, and the number of variables There are (3) variables included in the model, (2) independent variable and (1) dependent variable, as follows:-

Matrix of correlation coefficients for search variables

The relationship between the research variables was selected using the Pearson correlation method, where Table (4) indicates the results of this test, which showed the presence of varying correlations, at the level of statistical significance (level=0.05).

Table 4: Pearson correlation

Organizational agility	Short and long term planning	Planning using SWoT analysis	Planning using scenario	Variables
			1	Scenario planning
		1	0.862	Planning using swot analysis
	1	0.783	0.842	Short and long term planning
1	0.794	0.804	0.829	organizational agility

It will be clear from Table No. (4) the Pearson correlation matrix for the relationship between the three research variables that there is a correlation between planning using scenario analysis on the one hand and planning using SOWT analysis, short and long-term planning and organizational agility, where it came with a value of 0.862, 0.842, 0.801, 0.829 Straight.

While the values of Pearson Correlation between planning using sowt analysis on the one hand, short and long-term planning and organizational agility were 0.783, 0.804, respectively, while the value of Pearson Correlation between short and long-term planning on the one hand and organizational agility came with a value of 0.794, all of which are values that indicate a relationship between the research variables.

Research hypotheses test-:

1. First hypothesis test:

This hypothesis indicates the following:

It is possible for strategic planning practices to achieve organizational agility at the University of Baghdad, and for this test, the Kendall correlation coefficient was used, as well as the analysis of variance test between the variables of strategic planning practices and organizational agility. To find out the value of R2 and its significance, we refer to this through the tables (5, 6, and 7)

a) Kendall's correlation coefficient test:

It is clear from tables (5) to study the correlation through the "Kendall" correlation coefficient that there is a correlation between the independent variable "strategic planning practices", and the dependent variable "organizational agility", due to the presence of significant significance at the level of 0.05 between the two variables.

Table No. 5: Kendall's correlation coefficients between the variables of "strategic planning practices" and the variable "organizational agility"

dependent variable	Kendall's correlation coefficient		The independent variable
	sig	value	
organizational agility	0.004	0.809	strategic planning practices

*Statistically significant at the level of significance 0.05

b) Analysis of Variance:

It is clear from Table (6) to analyze the variance between the variables of strategic planning practices and organizational agility, that the value of the (f) test, which is statistically significant at the level of 0.05 significant and the degree of freedom of 144, indicates the validity of a relationship between the two variables.

Table No. 6: Results of the analysis of variance between the variable of strategic planning practices and the variable of organizational agility

test" F"		d.f.	mean squares	sum of squares	Statement	The independent variable x 1
sig	value`	144	243.654	23488.116	regression	strategic planning practices
0.004	119.210		2.431	376.655	the rest	

*Statistically significant at the level of significance 0.05

c) Regression analysis:

It is clear from Table (7) to study and analyze the regression between strategic planning practices and organizational agility that the value of the coefficient of determination (r^2) is equal to 0.654, and this means that strategic planning practices explain 65% of the value of organizational agility, while the rest is explained by other variables that were not included in the regression relationship. This, as the value of the "t-test" is equal to (0.332), and the value of morality is equal to (0.004), which is a statistical function and means that the independent variable strategic planning practices affects organizational agility, which is a substantial effect as the value of "t" did not reach zero.

Table 7: Results of the regression analysis between the variable "strategic planning practices" and the variable "organizational agility"

morale	t(Values)	Beta	R ²	standard error	B		independent variable
0.004	9.112		0.654	0.366	2.912	Constant	strategic planning practices
0.004	0.33320.021	0.021		0.053	0.397	X1	

*Statistically significant at the level of significance 0.05

We conclude from the study and analysis of the first hypothesis that the hypothesis is correct, that is, the strategic planning practices lead to achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.

1) The second hypothesis test:

This hypothesis states the following: "The more planning practices using scenario analysis, the more this leads to the achievement of organizational agility at the University of Baghdad. The study and testing of this hypothesis is illustrated through tables (8, 9, 10):

a) Kendall's correlation test

It is clear from the tables (8) to study the correlation through the "Kendall" correlation coefficient that there is a correlation between the independent variable "planning using scenario analysis", and the dependent variable "organizational agility", due to the presence of significant significance at the level of 0.05 between the two variables.

Table No. 8 Kendall's correlation coefficients between the variables of "planning using scenario analysis" and the variable "organizational agility"

dependent variable	Kendall's correlation coefficient		independent variable
	sig	value	
organizational agility	0.0011	0.829	Planning using scenario analysis

*Statistically significant at the level of significance 0.05

b) Analysis of Variance:

It is clear from Table (9) to analyze the variance between two planning variables using scenario analysis and organizational agility, that the value of the test (f) (118.965), which is statistically significant at the level of significant 0.05 and the degree of freedom of 142, indicates the validity of a relationship between the two variables.

Table No. 9: Results of the analysis of variance between the "planning using scenario" variable and the organizational agility variable

test" F"		d.f.	mean squares	sum of squares	Statement	The independent variable x 1
sig	value`	142	264.442	22287.541	regression	Planning using scenario analysis
0.0011	118.965		2.552	388.677	rest	

*Statistically significant at the level of significance 0.05

c) Regression analysis:

It is clear from Table (10) to study and analyze the regression between planning using the scenario and organizational agility that the value of the coefficient of determination (r²) is equal to 0.687. This means that planning using the scenario explains 69% of the organizational agility, while the rest is explained by other variables that were not included in the regression relationship. This, as the value of the "t-test" is equal to (0.356), and the value of morality is equal to (0.0011), which is a statistical function and means that the independent variable strategic planning practices affects organizational agility, which is a substantial effect as the value of "t" did not reach zero.

Table 10 the results of the regression analysis between the variable "planning using scenario" and the variable "organizational agility"

morale	t(Values)	Beta	R ²	standard error	B		independent variable
0.0011	8.644	-	0.687	0.402	2.981	Constant	Planning using scenario analysis
0.0011	0.356	0.019		0.058	0.411	X1	

*Statistically significant at the level of significance 0.05

We conclude from the study and analysis of the second hypothesis that the hypothesis is correct, that is, planning using the scenario leads to achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.

1) The third hypothesis test:

This hypothesis states the following: “The more planning practices using SOWT analysis, the more this leads to achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.” We explain the study and testing of this hypothesis through tables (11, 12, 13)

a) Kendall's correlation coefficient test:

It is clear from tables (11) to study the correlation through the "Kendall" correlation coefficient that there is a correlation between the independent variable "planning practices using SOWT analysis", and the dependent variable "organizational agility", due to the presence of significant significance at the level of 0.05 between the two variables.

Table No. (11): Kendall's correlation coefficients between the variables of "planning practices using SOWT analysis" and the variable "organizational agility"

dependent variable	Kendall's correlation coefficient		independent variable
	sig	value	
organizational agility	0.007	0.804	Planning Practices Using SOWT Analysis

*Statistically significant at the level of significance 0.05

b) Analysis of Variance:

It is evident from Table (12) to analyze the variance between the variables of planning practices using SOWT analysis and organizational agility, that the value of the test (f) is (117,955), which is statistically significant at a significant level of 0.05 and a degree of freedom of 144, and indicates the validity of a relationship between the two variables.

Table No. 12: Results of the analysis of variance between the variable of planning practices using SOWT analysis and the variable of organizational agility

test" F"		d.f.	mean squares	sum of squares	Statement	The independent variable x 1
sig	value`	144	266.820	21987,655	regression	Planning Practices Using SOWT Analysis
0.007	117,955		2.671	345,711	rest	

*Statistically significant at the level of significance 0.05

c) Regression analysis:

It is clear from Table (13) to study and analyze the regression between planning practices using SOWT analysis and organizational agility that the value of the coefficient of determination (r²) is equal to 0.646. This regression relationship, and the value of the "t-test" is equal to (0.371), and the value of morality is equal to (0.007), which is a statistical function and means that the

independent variable planning practices using SOWT analysis affects organizational agility, which is a significant effect as the value of "t" did not reach Zero.

Table 13: Results of the regression analysis between the variable "Planning practices using SOWT analysis" and the variable "Organizational agility"

morale	t(Values)	Beta	R ²	standard error	B		independent variable
0.007	9.112	-	0.646	0.382	2.455	Constant	Planning Practices Using SOWT Analysis
0.007	0.371	0.019		0.068	0.362	X1	

*Statistically significant at the level of significance 0.05

We conclude from the study and analysis of the third hypothesis that the hypothesis is correct, that is, planning practices using SOWT analysis lead to achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.

1) The fourth hypothesis test:

This hypothesis states the following: "The more short- and long-term planning practices increase, the more this leads to the achievement of organizational agility at the University of Baghdad." We explain the study and testing of this hypothesis through tables (14, 15, 16):

a) Kendall's correlation coefficient test:

It is clear from the tables (14) to study the correlation through the "Kendall" correlation coefficient that there is a correlation between the independent variable "short and long-term planning practices", and the dependent variable "organizational agility", due to the presence of significant significance at the level of 0.05 between the two variables.

Table No. 14: Kendall's correlation coefficients between the variables of "short and long-term planning practices" and the variable "organizational agility"

dependent variable	Kendall's correlation coefficient		independent variable
	sig	value	
organizational agility	0.003	0.794	Short and long-term planning practices

*Statistically significant at the level of significance 0.05

b) Analysis of Variance:

It is evident from Table (15) to analyze the variance between the variables of "short and long-term planning practices" and organizational agility, that the value of the (f) test, which is statistically significant at the level of 0.05 significant and the degree of freedom 142, indicates the validity of a relationship between the two variables.

Table No. 15: Results of the variance analysis between the variable of strategic planning practices and the variable of organizational agility

test " F "		d.f.	mean squares	sum of squares	Statement	The independent variable x 1
sig	value `	142	284.113	22392.117	regression	Short and long-term planning practices
	0.003	119.367	2.945	361.811	rest	

*Statistically significant at the level of significance 0.05

c) Regression analysis:

It is clear from Table (16) to study and analyze the regression between short and long-term planning practices and organizational agility that the value of the coefficient of determination (r^2) is equal to 0.630. This means that short and long-term planning practices explain 63% of organizational agility, while the rest is explained by other variables that have not It is included in this regression relationship, and the value of the "t" test is (0.391), and the value of morality is (0.003), which is a statistical function and means that the independent variable strategic planning practices affects organizational agility, which is a substantial effect as the "t" value did not reach to zero.

Table 16: Results of the regression analysis between the variable "strategic planning practices" and the variable "organizational agility"

morale	t(Values)	Beta	R ²	standard error	B		independent variable
0.003	9.855	-	0.630	0.344	2.416	Constant	Short and long-term planning practices
0.003	0.391	0.021		0.071	0.332	X1	

*Statistically significant at the level of significance 0.05

We conclude from the study and analysis of the fourth hypothesis that the hypothesis is correct, that is, short and long-term planning practices lead to achieving organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.

Summary of search results

- 1) It was found from the results at the level of testing the first hypothesis that there is a correct correlation between strategic planning practices and organizational agility at the University of Baghdad, where the value of this relationship reached at a confidence level of 0.05, 0.809 according to the Kendal correlation coefficient, which indicates that strategic planning practices are linked to achieving Organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.
- 2) The results of the current study confirmed that there is a significant impact of strategic planning practices at the University of Baghdad on organizational agility, reaching a value of 0.654, which is a fundamental value, which means that strategic planning practices at the University of Baghdad affect by 65% in achieving organizational agility at the

university, as shown by the results of the current study. The current study shows that strategic planning practices at the University of Baghdad depend on planning practices in terms of the dimensions of scenario analysis, SOWT analysis, short and long-term planning.

- 3) In light of the results of the study of the second hypothesis, it was found that there is an essential correlation between planning practices using scenario analysis at the University of Baghdad and organizational agility, where the value of this relationship reached at a confidence level of 0.05, 0.829 according to the Kendall correlation coefficient, which indicates that planning practices using Scenario analysis at the University of Baghdad is related to achieving organizational agility, and the results at the level of the second hypothesis also showed that there is a significant impact of planning practices using scenario analysis at the University of Baghdad on organizational agility, and it reached a value of 0.687, which is an essential value, which means that planning practices using analysis The scenario in the University of Baghdad affects by 69% in achieving organizational agility at the university, and from the results of the second hypothesis, it is also confirmed that planning practices using scenario analysis at the University of Baghdad are evident in practices, the most important of which are the analysis of scenarios related to the work environment, competitive environment, conditions of uncertainty in the university sector, Future changes, future risks and estimating the possibilities of their occurrence, alternatives to the image of the future of the university, assessment of the expected future impact on educational activities Me at the university.
- 4) In the third hypothesis, the results showed us the essential relationship between planning practices using SOWT analysis and organizational agility at the University of Baghdad, where the value of this relationship at a confidence level of 0.05 to 0.804 according to the Kendall correlation coefficient, which indicates that planning practices using SOWT analysis are related By achieving organizational agility, and from the results of analyzing the regression relationship between planning practices using SOWT analysis and organizational agility at the University of Baghdad, it was found that there is a significant impact of planning practices using SOWT analysis on organizational agility at the University of Baghdad, and its value reached 0.630, which is a fundamental value, which means that the practices of Planning using SOWT analysis affects 65% of organizational agility in government banks. The results also showed that planning practices using SOWT analysis at the university depend on the following aspects (identifying strengths and weaknesses, identifying opportunities and threats in educational services provided by the university, human resources strategy, its organizational procedures and the documentary cycle of its services, its competitive capabilities, follow-up and performance evaluation.
- 5) In the fourth hypothesis of the current study, it was found from the results that there is a significant relationship at a confidence level of 0.05 between short and long-term planning practices and organizational agility at the University of Baghdad, where the value of this relationship reached 0.794, according to the Kendall correlation coefficient, which indicates that planning practices are short And long-term linked to organizational agility at the University of Baghdad.

- 6) In the results of the study of the regression relationship between short and long-term planning practices and organizational agility at the university, it was found that there is a significant impact of short and long-term planning practices on organizational agility at the University of Baghdad, and its value reached 0.630, which is a substantial value, which means that short and long-term planning practices affect a percentage of 63% in achieving organizational agility at the university.
- 7) The results confirm that short- and long-term planning practices relate to the following practices: setting plans for educational activities and services, taking into account external and internal variables and including them in long- and short-term plans, developing a future vision for the university and working on it in the two-term, setting goals in the two-term, developing services educational development, the development of the financial resources of the university, the development of human resources policies and the performance of employees.
- 8) As for the results of the current study towards the dimensions of organizational agility at the University of Baghdad, it was confirmed by these results that they include: ease and speed of decision-making, speed of application of techniques and technology in its services, provision of appropriate resources for its activities in a timely manner, immediate response to emergency situations, speed of adjustment Its internal processes, the speed of assimilation of development in work methods, the speed of adjusting the documentary cycle, the speed of implementing the plans and programs of the instructional process, the speed of adjusting its plan in a timely manner.

Suggested practical recommendations

The researcher proposes a set of recommendations in light of the findings of the current study, which can help Iraqi universities in applying strategic planning and improving their levels of organizational agility, which are as follows:-

- 1) The university should direct its interests towards spreading the culture of strategic planning at all organizational and human levels, by developing appropriate training plans for this.
- 2) It is necessary for the university to work according to the method of strategic planning by analyzing scenarios, in order to build and anticipate different scenarios that affect areas related to the work environment, the competitive environment, as well as the conditions of uncertainty in Iraqi universities.
- 3) Iraqi universities should employ a method of strategic planning by analyzing scenarios to determine future changes and risks in the university sector, and to estimate the possibilities of their occurrence, while developing plans and alternatives to draw a picture of the future of the university.
- 4) Iraqi universities should work on applying the strategic planning method according to SOWT analysis, by focusing on identifying strengths and weaknesses, identifying opportunities and threats in the services provided by the university.

- 5) It is important for Iraqi universities to work on applying the strategic planning method according to SOWT analysis with regard to human resources, organizational procedures and the documentary cycle of its services, competitive capabilities, follow-up and performance evaluation.
- 6) Iraqi universities must rely on short and long-term planning practices in developing plans for educational activities and services, as well as taking into account external and internal variables.
- 7) It is important for Iraqi universities to work on planning to develop a future vision and strategic goals and to work on them in the two terms, in addition to planning in the short and long term to focus on developing human resources policies and employee performance.
- 8) It is necessary for Iraqi universities to work to enhance their organizational agility by focusing on emphasizing the ease and speed of decision-making, the speed of application of techniques and technology in their educational services.
- 9) The need to strengthen the institutional capacities of Iraqi universities towards the speedy provision of appropriate resources for their activities in a timely manner, as well as the immediate response to emergency situations facing them.

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